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Temple architecture: Classification and characteristics

Dr S Radhakrishnan¹

Abstract

Hindu temples are inexhaustible mines of Indian culture and tradition. They are not merely community prayer rooms or seats of deity. Rather, they are spiritual sources and primary carriers of Indian culture. It is clear from itihasa and Mahapurana references that the system of temple worship existed in ancient times. The Rameswara Pratishta of Sri Rama and the temple darshan of Rukmini Swayamvara indicate the same. In India there are many architectural forms for devalaya. Vastuvidya classified the temples geographically. Every architecture style has its own uniqueness and methodology. Vastu follows a peculiar pattern which is proportional, symmetrical design for temples. Here the paper examines the basic vastu principles of temple construction and classification of temple architecture

Keywords

Vaṣṭu, Temple Architecture, Hindu Temple, Prasada

Introduction

Temples are the crown jewels of Indian architecture. Considering this importance, many books have been written exclusively on the rules of temple construction in Indian architecture. Tantra Samuccaya² and Shilpa Ratna - Kerala scriptures are also famous among them. Indian architectural tradition continues to amaze even abroad with the impact of its temple constructions and sculptures. These structures, which would be impossible for human beings even with the help of modern

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2 Tantra Samuccaya silpa bhaga of Chennas Narayanan Nampoothiri. Silparatna of Srikumara is the famous Sanskrit text that deals with devalaya vastu. Kerala temple architecture mainly follows these two texts

machines, are the embodiment of architectural beauty concepts that have survived the wrath of nature and foreign invasions.

Categories of Prasada

Although the various temple construction methods in India are different, their basic principle is the same. Architecture Indian temples are classified into three categories based on garbhagriha, antaralam, mandapam, shikharam and gopuram. The Prasads mainly divided as three are named Nagara, Dravida and Vesara

Nagara

Nagara types of temples are found in the terrain from the Himalayas to the Vindhya Mountains. Odisha, Solanki and Khajuraho methods are its variants. A rectangular garbhagriha is built on a raised base with steps around it. It also has the highest peak. The rounded spires are attached to the amalaka and kalasa ornaments. Puri Jagannath Temple, Khajuraho Vishwanath Temple and Lakshmana Temple are fine examples of Nagara style. There are other subtypes of this style, differing in the number and construction of the pinnacles. If all the limb parts from Paduka to Stupika are square then it is Nagara Prasadalakshana. 'Koota' and 'sala' are important in this. There can be special columns and multiple floors. But there are no 'nasika' decorations like others.

Dravida

The South Indian style or Dravidian style is mainly the style of the areas between the Krishna and Kaveri rivers. Unlike the Nagara temples, these are surrounded by a boundary wall which is called 'mahamaryada'. The style is characterized by the tall Nagara shikhara-like vimanas or gopuras located at its main entrances. The part above this is referred to as sikhara in Dravidian style. Dravida Gopurams are square in contrast to 'Nagara Shikhara' style. Dwarapalakas and gopura with different sculptures is also a feature of this style. Apart from the square shape, other shapes like circle, hexagon, octagon, apsidal (gajaprishta), oval etc are also adopted in this style. The large temple pond and sub-shrines adjacent to the temple are also important in Dravidian style. Kerala temple construction is also the part of 'dravida' with some peculiar design. From the paduka or gala top is

six-cornered or eight-cornered, it is Dravidaprasada. The 'kuta' can be more important than the 'kosta'. There can be various decorations like 'bhadrā nasika' in the middle parts of the shalas. The 'koota' can be round, octagonal or square in shape.

Vesara

Vesara style is the style of the region from the Vindhya Mountains to the banks of the Krishna River. It is a blend of Nagara and Dravidian styles. The name Chalukya style is also apt as the Chalukyas were the main builders. Temples of this style are mostly found in North Karnataka. Badami and Virupaksha temples are prominent among those built in this style. Similarly, vesara is also commonly used for circular prasadas as from the paduka. The prasada shikhara and koota should be fairly rounded. Thus according to the prasads, the pratisthabheda has also been mentioned there. Sarupa idols of Soumyamurthys are placed in Nagara Prasada, the idols with vehicle-like chariots and horses are in Dravida Prasada, for couples and dance figures of idols Vesara Prasad are special. There is also a rule to do without these classifications. Apart from Nagara Dravida vesara difference there are other divisions such as Shantika, Paushtika, Jayadam, Miravala and Sarvakamikam also there depending on their construction. Devalaya vastu texts deal with hundreds of different temple styles by decorations and other peculiarities.

Generally, prasads are made in seven different shapes such as circle, ellipse, rectangle, square, hexagon, octagon and apsidal (hasti prastha /gajaprastha). There are other types of jati, chhandam, vikalpam and abhasam temples also described by the parisha order. Jati Prasad has six types ranging from eleven 'kol' parisha to seventy 'kol' parisha. The floors are different accordingly. Apart from this, Chanda Prasads ranging from thirteen to sixty-six Parishas³, Vikalpa Prasads is ranging from nine to fifty-six Parishas, Abhasa Prasads ranging from eleven to forty-eight Parishas and their six variants each, starting from one floor and making twelve floors. There are more than a thousand variants available.

3. Parisa- parisa is a categorisation of temples as per their size. Parisa is based on the width of the main srikovil, and the temple complex designed by the same proportion.

The temple worship system is important among the various upasana schemes that exist for the spiritual elevation of man. Upasana according to Hindu Dharma are noted here.

“कृते श्रुत्युक्त आचाराः, नेतायां स्मृति संभवः ।
द्वापरे तु पुराणोक्ताः, कलावागम सम्मतः ।”

According to the instruction, the method of upasana in this age is tantric, and temple worship based on that. If we look at the temples scientifically, they are not just buildings for worship but are the visible prototypes of the cosmic body and the physical body. This is what the Tantra Shastra expression “Deho Devalaya : Jivo Deva Sadasiva:” indicates. Temples symbolize not only the gross body but also the subtle body.

This will be clear if we look carefully at the construction of the temple. The five boundaries (panchaprakaras) Maha maryada, bahyahara, madhyahara, antahara and antarmandalam refer to the gross body of the deity and the sanctum sanctorum, deva pratishtha and shadadharas refer to the subtle body. Some Vastu texts refer to these prakaras as the body of the deity. The text ‘Vishwakarmya’ thus imagines the garbhagriha as the head, the inner altar as the face, the mandapam as the neck-gala, the four sides as the arms, the outer circumambulatory path as the stomach-kukshi position, the outer wall as the knees and the gopurams as the foot.

In this way, it can be seen that the temple has a proportional growth that represents the gross body part, depending on the temple construction. And the gross body is the place of the deva complex consisting of the ten devathas who are the Dikpalakas, saptamata, Veerabhadra and Ganapati. Temple sacrificial stones are symbols of these devatas. Deity has not only external forms but also a subtle body which is not visible to us. The deity in the sanctum sanctorum is not only the idol that we see but also the shadadhara placed below. Shadadhara Pratishtha consists of Aadharashila, Nidhikumbha, Padma, Kurma, Yoganala and Napumsakasila. At the beginning of the construction of the temple, a pit is dug in the consecrated ground and the foundation stone is placed and a Nidhikumbha filled with precious stones is fixed in the center of the pit. Ashta dalapadma made of stone

should be placed on top of it and Kurma should be placed on top of it. Moreover, the yoganala, which is a symbol of the celestial body, with an empty interior and a pointed tip pipe, and a napumaka sila should be placed on top of it. The mantras used to invoke the deity in normal pujas are of this concept.

This shadadhara commandment refers to the chakras of the subtle body. Mooladhara-Svadhithana Chakra which is the base stone, Nidhi Kumbha which is Manipuraka, Padma and Kurma which is Anahata Chakra, Yoganala in the concept of Vishudhi Chakra and beyond that the napumaka sila is in Ajna Chakra which is a symbol of Parabrahmachaitanya. The deity represents the Sahasrara Padma. Temple construction is usually done in positions known to have the presence of diety. Apart from this, proper land for worship is determined and consecrated and temple construction is still practiced today. Renovation of ancient temples is also an architectural subject. It is called by jeernoddhara.

The location of the new temple should be made possible with the prescribed rulings of the Shastras. Appropriate design of Prasada should be determined by land assessment and other ways dealt by the sastra. Based on that, Deva Pratishtha should be done in appropriate measure along with all ornamental designs. But if the temple is placed by great seers or a Swayambhu idol, there is no importance in land selection rules etc. Otherwise the temple size generally determines the size of idol or the idol size should be determined from the size of prasadas. The point is that it should be accepted according to the importance of prasada or idol. If the temple is completely or partially destroyed by weather, air, fire, or water, it is ruled that the old dimensions or materials should not be changed during the renovation. But when it is not fulfilled without changing in some way, it can be changed into similar or superior things. If this kind of reconstruction work is done, a balalaya should be made in the Isana kone(north east)corner of the main prasada, or vayukone (north West) or nirtri (south west) and a temporary poojas should be made there to complete the work of the moola prasad. Balalaya can be constructed with temporary construction materials or with mud or wood. As it is not advisable to keep the deity in the balayala for a long

time, the prasada preparation should be completed immediately.

Balalaya should occupy two-thirds, three-fifths or five-ninths of the Mulalaya area. The size of the idol should also be determined by the above factors in the original idol. Balabimba should be made of metal, clay or wood. Commonly stones are not used for balabimba, because after the re-installation of the deity, the balabimba should be left as per the rule. In such a case, if the stone has to be immersed in water, Tantra Shastra considers it as one of the most harmful things to find and enshrine the same stone at some point. This rule is followed to prevent that from happening. On the other hand, it is clear that after re-consecration, when the metal is melted and wood is burnt, the object does not remain in its original form. Construction is not done completely in the Mulalaya, there is no need to do the Balalaya. The work can be done by performing Pancharapratishta.

All solid and undamaged old stone and wood can be used for restoration work. But the construction of a new temple requires new materials. It is not advisable to add old materials while making new ones. There is a ruling that only if the temple is destroyed due to reasons such as river, sea, storm etc., the temple can be built and installed in any direction other than Vayu, Agni, Nirriti, South, within a thousand 'daṇḍ' from that place. It should be relocated to a place where there is no chance of the above-mentioned dangers occurring later. There are vastu rules about replacing the temple idol in this way. Only if the parts are disintegrating and perishing is it enough to change the idol. If the shapes are cut, it is enough to mold them there. Idols that have a supernatural background or ancient presence should be tied up and protected even if the body itself is cut. It is the rule that such idols should not be changed even if they become decayed. If for some reason the old bimba is lost, another similar one should be made. Sankochakriya is there if there is no damage to the idol or within a year all the repairs will be completed, otherwise the bimba will definitely have to be moved out.

Construction of Temple

Hindu temple construction is an amalgamation of many Indian sciences. The most important of them is architecture. The basis of

sculpture is the earth we live on. That is the concept of Vastu Purusha. It is the one which encompasses the whole of the earth, but which is subtly subtle. The construction of Madhya Khanda, ideal for devalaya and it should be avoided in manushyalaya, is the most important structural difference.

Temples also have appropriate land determination rules, as do the texts prescribed for house sitting. It essentially says. A place for the temple can be constructed near the shrine, on the river bank, on the seashore, at the confluence of rivers, in the mountains, in the valleys, in the forests, sub-forests, in the gardens, in the sage gardens, in the village, in the royal city, in the port city, in any other beautiful area, where there is a presence or concept of the deity, temples should be constructed in suitable places for the gods in these lands. The land should be leveled and purified physically and strategically and accepted by Vastu Puja and Vastubali. After digging in the brahma pada, the base stone and the shadha dharas should be placed in a suitable manner, and the floor should be levelled so that only the tip of the yoganala is visible.

After this is garbhanyasa. It should be placed under the leg before starting the construction of the uterine wall. After that, the construction of Srikovil and Garbhagriha starts. Sometimes Srikovil itself can become a garbhagruha. Srikovils are often built with many storeys and different shapes. Square, circle, octagon, hexagone, apsidal, oval are the common shapes found in the construction. In this circle and square are mostly found. First of all, for the construction of the temple, the Prasada area should be determined by assigning the appropriate shape to the deity. Yoni⁴ - Mathematical calculation as per vastu- should be determined based on direction. Vrishabhayoni is usually adopted for east-facing temples and Dhvajayoni for west-facing ones. Otherwise, it should be selected accordingly. Yoni concept applies to all the major parts in temple construction. Even the idols for installation must be apt as per this system of measurement.

⁴ Yoni – yoni or aya formula defining the breadth measurement is useful for construction connected to the cardinal directions. Dwaja, dooma, simha, swana, vrushbha, khara, gaja and vayasa are the certain symbols of the direction from west. Odd numbers are used for good construction.

If the prasadam including the floor is assigned to the human body, then its head or the chandramandalam is the Srikovi or the Garbhagriha. Except for small prasads, the rest of the garbhagriha should be slightly elevated from the floor of the shrine. It is also composed of the five vargas like Padi, Galam, Kumudam, Jagati and Padukam. As its amshakrama (proportion) and vinyasa (arrangement) are also of importance in order, it is more than an ornament in design.

It is on the surface of this foundation that Srikovil, which is called Somamandala, should be worked. If the sreekovil and the garbhagruha are separate, the space between them is usually constructed as a corridor. If it is small, instead of this corridor, a wall of the same width can be made. The size is important in the construction of the inside measure of garbhagruha and outside of the srikovil. Wall made of materials such as Krishna Shila with ornamental work like kallutthara (beam of stone) and other decorations. On top of that, a crown-shaped roof should be placed and above that, a dome in the shape of a bud of a lotus flower named thazhikakudam. All these also represent the canon of Indian Yoga, Tantra and other Shastras.

Conclusion

According to vastuvidya, temple construction is always related to the deity. All architecture styles follow the same method for making garbhagruha and other basic structural designs. Designs are developed regionally and materials are also locally available are used for construction. Dravida, Nagara and Vesara types of temples are the main attractions of temple architecture all over India.

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